

A p-type Cu_2O photoanode for solar water oxidation

Graphical abstract

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In brief

By incorporating selective contacts, a p-type Cu_2O photoanode demonstrated a record photocurrent, establishing the best performance to date for oxide semiconductors in solar water oxidation. This work highlights that judicious interface engineering can facilitate the use of p-type semiconductors as photoanodes, thereby expanding the range of available semiconductor materials for photo(electro)catalytic oxidation reactions.

Highlights

- Charge-selective contacts enable the use of p-type Cu_2O as an efficient photoanode
- Record photocurrent density of 8.65 mA cm^{-2} for metal oxide photoanodes under 1 sun
- Cu_2O photoanodes exhibited stable water oxidation in alkaline and neutral electrolytes

Article

A p-type Cu₂O photoanode for solar water oxidation

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CONTEXT & SCALE Splitting water with sunlight can generate clean hydrogen fuel, but oxide photoanodes have so far struggled to combine high current output with long-term stability. In this work, we demonstrate that cuprous oxide (Cu₂O)—a simple and earth-abundant semiconductor typically used for hydrogen production—can instead be applied to oxygen generation when equipped with carefully designed “selective contacts” that direct charge carriers efficiently. Using a Ga₂O₃/TiO₂/indium tin oxide (ITO) back contact and an ultrathin Al₂O₃/Au front contact with a NiFe oxyhydroxide catalyst, the optimized device achieved a photocurrent of 8.65 mA cm⁻² at 1.23 V vs. the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) in alkaline electrolyte, with nearly 100% Faradaic efficiency and stable operation for 30 h. These findings demonstrate that the conventional association between semiconductor doping type and its role in photoelectrochemical devices can be broken, thereby enabling p-type oxides to serve effectively as photoanodes.

SUMMARY

The development of efficient, stable, and earth-abundant photoanodes for solar water oxidation is critical to advancing photoelectrochemical and photocatalytic systems for large-scale renewable fuel production. Here, we demonstrate that p-type Cu₂O, typically studied as a photocathode material, can be used as a high-performance photoanode through judicious engineering of charge carrier-selective contacts on thermally oxidized Cu₂O sheets. The introduction of Ga₂O₃, TiO₂, and indium tin oxide (ITO) layers as an electron-selective back contact, combined with Al₂O₃, Au, and Ni front layers, significantly enhanced charge separation and electron transfer. The champion Cu₂O photoanode exhibited a photocurrent density of 8.65 mA cm⁻² at 1.23 V vs. the reversible hydrogen electrode in alkaline media, which is the highest reported for metal oxide photoanodes. These findings highlight the pivotal role of charge carrier-selective interface engineering in broadening the scope of available semiconductor materials for photo(electro)catalytic oxidation reactions, irrespective of the doping type of the light-absorbing material.

INTRODUCTION

Earth-abundant metal oxide semiconductors are considered promising materials for solar water splitting due to their economic feasibility in device fabrication. In general, n-type metal oxide semiconductors, such as Fe₂O₃ (2.1 eV),^{1–3} BiVO₄ (2.4 eV),^{4–6} and WO₃ (2.6 eV),^{7–9} have been extensively studied as photoanode candidates for solar water oxidation. These n-type semiconductors are well known for forming favorable upward band bending at the semiconductor/electrolyte interface, with a suitable valence band edge positioned below the water oxidation potential, facilitating efficient hole transfer.¹⁰ Despite significant improvements in photoelectrochemical (PEC) efficiency that have been achieved with n-type metal oxide semiconductors, challenges remain in achieving high photocurrent densities comparable to those observed in PEC hydrogen evolu-

tion using p-type photocathodes such as Sb₂Se₃, InP, and Si (>15 mA cm⁻²).^{11–14} For example, the relatively large band gap of n-type semiconductors limits the theoretical maximum photocurrent density (<8 mA cm⁻² for BiVO₄),¹⁵ and the short minority carrier diffusion lengths (~100 nm for BiVO₄ and ~4 nm for Fe₂O₃) and low carrier mobility restrict the photoelectrode thickness to less than 200 nm, thereby reducing light absorption.^{16–19} Furthermore, the synthesis of metal oxides on conductive glass substrates (e.g., fluorine-doped tin oxide and indium tin oxide [ITO]) often requires low-temperature processing (<500°C) due to their low thermal stability.²⁰ This results in small grain sizes and low crystallinity of metal oxide semiconductors, which in turn promote rapid charge recombination and low carrier mobility.^{21,22}

In the case of p-type Cu₂O, its relatively small band gap (2.0 eV) allows for a theoretical maximum photocurrent density

of up to 14.9 mA cm⁻². Its exceptionally long carrier diffusion length (3–10 μm), high mobility (~100 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹), and high light absorption coefficient (>10⁵ cm⁻¹) also enable the use of a sufficient thickness of Cu₂O for effective light absorption.^{23–25} These distinct properties offer higher photoconversion efficiency compared with n-type semiconductors. However, the properties of p-type semiconductors typically result in a downward band bending at the semiconductor/electrolyte junction, leading to its predominant application in hydrogen evolution reaction rather than in water oxidation. Some studies have attempted to use Cu₂O as a photoanode for water oxidation by synthesizing n-type Cu₂O^{26,27} or by forming an ohmic contact with an Au overlayer,²⁸ but challenges such as low crystallinity, non-selective carrier transfer, and high charge recombination at the interface still remain.

The importance of charge-selective contacts is well established in photovoltaic (PV) devices for improving the solar conversion efficiency, yet the concept is rarely applied in photocatalytic systems. In one such example, Gurudayal et al.²⁹ demonstrated that n-type Si, typically used as a photoanode, could be used as a photocathode for PEC carbon dioxide reduction through the use of charge-selective contacts.²⁹ Drawing inspiration from this work, we aimed to enable the use of high-quality p-type Cu₂O, typically used as a photocathode, to be used as a photoanode for water oxidation through the application of charge-selective contacts. Thermal oxidation of Cu metal foil facilitates the synthesis of a semiconductor sheet without the need for an additional conductive substrate, allowing the production of highly crystalline Cu₂O through high-temperature synthesis (>1,000°C). Furthermore, judicious selection of an electron-selective contact composed of Ga₂O₃ and TiO₂,^{30–32} along with the surface state passivation layer of Al₂O₃ and hole transport layer of Au, were employed to provide effective charge separation and high solar water oxidation photocurrents. Our approach achieved a photocurrent density of 8.65 mA cm⁻² at 1.23 V vs. the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) for solar water oxidation. To the best of our knowledge, this is the highest value reported for metal oxide photoanodes. Our study reveals a new opportunity to broaden the range of applicable semiconductor materials for PEC and photocatalytic systems regardless of their doping type.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of the p-type Cu₂O photoanode

For the preparation of p-type Cu₂O photoanodes, we synthesized a Cu₂O sheet via thermal oxidation of Cu foils, followed by an etching process with aqueous ammonia solution.³⁰ First, cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were performed to confirm the synthesis of thermally oxidized Cu₂O. In the cross-sectional SEM and EDX measurements, the untreated Cu foil exhibited approximately 61.2% Cu and 4.5% O content (atomic percent), whereas the thermally oxidized Cu₂O sample showed elemental compositions of 54.6% Cu and 25.3% O, consistent with the expected 2:1 atomic ratio of Cu to O for Cu₂O

(Figure S1). The XPS analysis further supported this result, as the Cu 2p region showed no characteristic Cu²⁺ satellite peaks typically associated with CuO, confirming that Cu₂O was successfully formed via thermal oxidation of the Cu foil (Figure S2). The Mott-Schottky plot revealed the p-type character of the Cu₂O semiconductor with a flat-band potential of 0.95 V vs. RHE (Figures S3 and S4). The effect of ammonia etching was investigated through top-view SEM images. The pristine Cu₂O sheet exhibited a distinct crystal morphology after etching, revealing a variety of crystallographic orientations (Figure S5).³⁰

Subsequently, overlayers for facile electron and hole transport were deposited on the respective sides of the Cu₂O sheet using vacuum deposition methods such as atomic layer deposition (ALD), physical vapor deposition (PVD), and magnetron sputtering. First, a 15 nm Ga₂O₃ and a 100 nm TiO₂ overlayer were sequentially deposited by ALD, followed by deposition of a 150 nm ITO layer using PVD to form a conductive contact layer. Ag paste was painted on top of the ITO layer in a square pattern, and then Cu metal was attached to form the contact. The front layer, driving water oxidation, involved depositing a 1 nm Al₂O₃ layer via ALD, followed by the sequential deposition of 100 nm Au and 50 nm Ni by sputtering. Finally, the fabricated Cu₂O sheet was placed on a glass slide and packaged with non-conductive epoxy to prevent corrosion and a short circuit between the back contact and the electrolyte solution, as well as to improve the mechanical stability of the thermally oxidized Cu₂O, which is fragile at low thickness (Figures 1 and S6).

Characterizations of the overlayers on the Cu₂O photoanode

The overlayers were characterized through SEM measurements, observing changes in both the morphology of the back contacts (Figure S7) and the front layers (Figure S8). The thickness and deposition of each layer were further verified by cross-sectional transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and EDX analysis. The cross-sectional TEM showed conformal layers of the 15 nm Ga₂O₃, 100 nm TiO₂, 150 nm ITO on the back contact (Figures 2A–2E), and the 100 nm Au and 50 nm Ni layers were also well-deposited on the front layer of the Cu₂O sheet (Figures 2F–2J). The 1 nm Al₂O₃ layer was too thin to be observed directly (Figure 2H), but its presence was confirmed through XPS and cross-sectional TEM/EDX analyses. In the XPS analysis, we identified the Al 2p doublet on the Cu₂O electrode with the 1 nm Al₂O₃ layer at 74.7 and 77.1 eV (Figure S9A), and cross-sectional TEM/EDX confirmed the conformal deposition of the Al₂O₃ layer on the Cu₂O surface (Figure S10). Additionally, when the 100 nm Au and 50 nm Ni layers were further deposited, the Au 4f and Ni 2p doublets appeared, while the peaks of the underlying layers disappeared (Figures S9B and S9C). In the XPS measurements of the back contact layers, Ga 2p (1,118.1 eV), Ti 2p (458.4 and 464.2 eV), and In 3d (444.4 and 452.0 eV) peaks corresponding to Ga₂O₃, TiO₂, and ITO were also observed (Figure S11). The peaks of the underlying layers disappeared in these measurements, as shown in the XPS analysis of the front layers, indicating conformal and uniform deposition of each layer.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the preparation of the p-type Cu_2O photoanode

(A) Preparation of back contact layers. The back contact layers were sequentially prepared with 15 nm Ga_2O_3 , 100 nm TiO_2 , and 150 nm ITO.

(B) Preparation of front layers. The front layers were fabricated with 1 nm Al_2O_3 , 100 nm Au, and 50 nm Ni.

(C) Electrode packaging after the deposition of each layer. The Cu_2O sheet was covered with non-conductive epoxy on a glass slide to construct the p-type Cu_2O photoanode.

PEC performance of Cu_2O photoanodes for water oxidation

Next, we evaluated the photoelectrode for water oxidation by measuring the PEC performance. To facilitate water oxidation, we formed a nickel-iron oxyhydroxide co-catalyst on the Ni layer of the front contact. The co-catalyst was formed using a galvanic replacement method with Fe^{2+} solution (Figure S12).³³ First, we investigated the Fe^{2+} treatment on a Ni-coated fluorine-doped

tin oxide (FTO) and FTO/Au surface. The electrochemical water oxidation kinetics were then evaluated in 1 M KOH solution (pH 14) using cyclic voltammetry (CV). In the CV measurement, the Fe^{2+} -treated Ni electrode exhibited an improved onset potential and current density (Figure S13). Notably, the Ni-coated FTO/Au electrode showed a slightly improved onset potential compared with its counterpart on the bare FTO substrate, likely due to the highly electronegative Au substrate facilitating more efficient

Figure 2. Cross-sectional TEM measurement of the Cu_2O photoanode

(A) Cross-sectional high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) micrograph of the back contact layers on the Cu_2O photoanode.

(B–E) Elemental mapping of Cu, Ga, Ti, and In, respectively.

(F) Cross-sectional HAADF micrograph of the front layers on the Cu_2O photoanode.

(G–J) Elemental mapping of Cu, Al, Au, and Ni, respectively.

Figure 3. PEC performance evaluation of Cu₂O photoanodes in water oxidation

(A) LSV measurement of Cu₂O photoanodes with an Fe²⁺ treatment on the Ni surface in 1 M KOH (pH 14) under 1 sun illumination from a solar simulator.

(B) Three-electrode ABPE analysis obtained from the LSV curve under 1 sun illumination from a solar simulator.

(C) IPCE measurement of the Cu₂O photoanode with Fe²⁺ treatment at 1.23 V vs. RHE. The IPCE was performed using monochromatic light generated from a halogen light source (plus a constant 5% white light bias from an light-emitting diode [LED]).

(D and E) Stability test and O₂ measurement of the Cu₂O photoanode at 1.23 V vs. RHE. In the O₂ measurement, the black lines represent theoretical O₂ evolution (i.e., 100% Faradaic efficiency) as calculated from the photocurrent in the CA measurement (Figure S24), while the green circles represent the measured O₂ evolution determined from gas chromatography. The GC measurement was carried out using a white light LED to achieve a photocurrent comparable to that obtained under 1 sun illumination from a solar simulator.

charge transfer.^{34,35} In addition, the Fe²⁺-treated Ni electrode exhibited increased surface roughness after the galvanic treatment, but negligible morphological changes were observed after chronoamperometry (CA) measurements used to monitor their activation process (Figures S14–S16). These observations suggest that the co-catalyst is activated in the form of NiFe oxyhydroxide (NiFeOOH), rather than forming a layered double hydroxide (LDH) structure from as-prepared NiFe(OH)_x. Based on this result, we also treated a Ni surface of the packaged Cu₂O photoanode in the same manner to improve the PEC water oxidation efficiency. XPS, high-resolution cross-sectional TEM, and EDX analyses further confirmed the formation of the NiFe co-catalyst on the Ni surface after Fe²⁺ treatment, without any significant changes observed in the underlying layers (Figures S17–S19).

We evaluated PEC water oxidation through a comparative analysis of Cu₂O photoanodes with and without Fe²⁺ treatment using linear sweep voltammetry (LSV). LSV measurements were performed after prior CV cycling to confirm activation of each co-catalyst (i.e., nickel and nickel-iron oxyhydroxides) (Figure S20). After the activation process, nickel oxyhydroxides showed negligible changes (Figure S21A), whereas nickel-iron oxyhydroxides exhibited improved photocurrent and fill factor following continuous CV cycling (Figure S21B). Accordingly, all

subsequent PEC measurements were conducted after first activating the nickel-iron oxyhydroxides (denoted as NiFe) on the photoanode surface with a surface area of ~0.1–0.12 cm². In LSV measurements, the Fe²⁺-treated electrode showed enhanced onset potential and photocurrent density in PEC water oxidation compared with the untreated electrode. Specifically, the onset potential was improved from 1.04 to 0.74 V vs. RHE (Figure S20), and the photocurrent density at 1.23 V increased from 5.04 to 8.65 mA cm⁻² (Figures 3A and S21A). To ensure the reliability of the PEC performance for the Cu₂O photoanode, more than 18 devices were tested to confirm statistical relevance, and an average photocurrent density of 7.64 mA cm⁻² was obtained (Figure S22). The half-cell applied bias photon-to-current efficiency (ABPE) was 1.72% at 0.91 V vs. RHE (Figure 3B). The incident photon-to-current efficiency (IPCE) showed a steep rise from 640 nm, reaching about 90% at 520 nm and then falling linearly to about 40% for the shorter wavelengths, a phenomenon that was observed previously.³² The integrated photocurrent matched with the photocurrent density measured in the LSV (Figure 3C), and it showed 87.5% injection efficiency with respect to MeOH oxidation (Figure S23). Furthermore, CA measurement demonstrated that the fabricated Cu₂O photoanode was able to perform stable water

Figure 4. PEC performance of Cu_2O photoanodes with different back contact layer configurations

(A) LSV curves of Cu_2O photoanodes modified with various back contact layers, including ITO, ITO/ Ga_2O_3 , ITO/ TiO_2 , and ITO/ $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3$. All electrodes featured an identical front layer consisting of $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}/\text{NiFe}$.

(B) EIS analysis of the Cu_2O photoanodes in the MF region to investigate the electron transport resistance from the Cu_2O to ITO back contact.

(C) EIS analysis of the Cu_2O photoanodes in the LF region to investigate the charge transfer resistance during the water oxidation reaction.

oxidation at 1.23 V vs. RHE for 30 h (Figure 3D), with a $\sim 100\%$ Faradaic efficiency (Figures 3E and S24). The time delay following the first gas chromatography (GC) measurement in Figure 3E is due to the time required for the evolved gas to fill and reach a steady state within the reactor and the tubing to the gas chromatograph following an initial purging step (more details in Methods).

The role of back contact layers for electron-selective transport in facilitating water oxidation

A high photocurrent density of 8.65 mA cm^{-2} at 1.23 V vs. RHE was achieved with a p-type Cu_2O semiconductor. To determine the design principles that enable this, we conducted additional control experiments. First, we investigated the effect of different configurations for the back contact layers affecting electron transport/transfer within the Cu_2O photoanode. Four different back contact layers—ITO, ITO/ Ga_2O_3 , ITO/ TiO_2 , and ITO/ $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3$ —were fabricated with the identical front-layer configuration (i.e., $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}/\text{NiFe}$). The efficiency of PEC water oxidation was evaluated through LSV measurement. In the LSV measurement, significant differences in PEC performance were observed depending on the back contact layers, following the order: ITO/ $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3 > \text{ITO}/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3 > \text{ITO}/\text{TiO}_2 > \text{ITO}$ (Figures 4A and S25). While the Cu_2O photoanode with only a conductive ITO back contact layer exhibited negligible photoactivity in water oxidation in the potential range measured, the Cu_2O modified with Ga_2O_3 and TiO_2 showed enhanced PEC performance in terms of both onset potential and photocurrent density. We speculate that these improvements are attributed to the formation of an electron-selective contact on the Cu_2O , facilitated by the proper band positions of Ga_2O_3 and TiO_2 . However, it is noteworthy that the ITO/ TiO_2 layer showed much lower PEC efficiency compared with the ITO/ Ga_2O_3 layer, even though TiO_2 has a conduction band edge position that is suitable for electron transfer.^{31,36} This suggests that fewer defects are present at the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3$ interface as compared with the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{TiO}_2$ interface, which reduces recombination.

To determine the presence of interface defects, we carried out electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis to inves-

tigate the effect of each back contact layer on charge carrier transport/transfer within the Cu_2O semiconductor. Nyquist plots for each sample with different back contact layers were measured across a voltage range relevant to PEC water oxidation and fitted using a 3- $[\text{RC}_{\text{parallel}}]$ (all in series) equivalent circuit (Figures S26 and S27).³⁷ We obtained capacitance and resistance values in different frequency regions at each applied voltage, and comparative analyses were performed. The data were classified into high-frequency (HF), medium-frequency (MF), and low-frequency (LF) regions based on the magnitude of capacitance values, and the determined resistance within the same frequency regions was compared (Figure S28). In the HF region, we could observe for all measured samples similar resistance and capacitance values (only for a photoanode without the ITO layer showed higher resistance, $\sim 100 \text{ ohm cm}^2$) (Figure S29). This represents the resistivity at the back contact, including charge transport and contact resistance to the copper wire.

While the ITO/ Ga_2O_3 showed an MF resistance in the range of 30 ohm cm^2 , both photoanodes with ITO/ TiO_2 and ITO/ $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3$ reached an MF resistance of 100 ohm cm^2 . We found that these trends of resistance matched well with the fill factor in the LSV curves, indicating that higher MF resistance leads to lower fill factors (Figures 4B and S30). Therefore, the result suggests that the MF resistance represents a series resistance at the interface between the Cu_2O and the overlayer. The resistance in the LF region resembled the shape of the photocurrent of each photoanode under illumination, and this represents therefore the charge transfer resistance to the electrolyte solution during the water oxidation reaction (Figure 4C). In our EIS data, all of the photoanodes showed a sharp resistance decrease near their respective onset potential regions observed in the LSV measurements (Figure 4A). It is well established that charge transfer resistance under PEC conditions often exhibits a sharp drop at the onset potential region, which indicates the initiation of water oxidation.^{38,39} Furthermore, the associated high capacitance in the range of mF cm^{-2} also clearly indicates the known high capacitance of (oxy)hydroxide-based co-catalysts such as NiO_x , RuO_2 , or CoPi .⁴⁰

Figure 5. PEC performance of Cu₂O photoanodes with different front-layer configurations

(A) LSV curves of the Cu₂O photoanodes modified with three different front layers of Cu₂O, Cu₂O/NiFe, and Cu₂O/Au/NiFe.

(B) LSV curves of the Cu₂O photoanodes with an additional 1 nm Al₂O₃ layer on the Cu₂O surface. All electrodes featured an identical back contact layer of ITO/TiO₂/Ga₂O₃.

(C) Comparative analysis of PEC performance for Cu₂O photoanodes with different front-layer configurations.

Based on our analysis, we assign the distinct roles of the back contact layers comprising Ga₂O₃, TiO₂, and ITO. In the case of Ga₂O₃, the band positions enable selective electron transfer, thereby reducing recombination at the interface. Moreover, the highly reactive ALD precursor chemically reduces surface CuO back to Cu₂O, as the Cu₂O surface is typically oxidized upon brief exposure to air while transferring the sample to the ALD chamber.^{41,42} This removal of CuO minimizes trap states that could result in charge recombination at the interface between Cu₂O and the back contact layers, explaining its higher PEC performance compared with photoanodes with the ITO/TiO₂. When TiO₂ was deposited directly on Cu₂O, it exhibited a lower PEC performance than the photoanode with Ga₂O₃. However, the TiO₂ layer showed significant improvement when combined with Ga₂O₃. This enhancement is likely due to the relatively thick TiO₂ layer, which not only provides an efficient junction for electron transfer but also likely prevents a shunt pathway between Cu₂O and ITO (Figure S31).^{43,44} Lastly, the ITO layer does not directly contribute to forming a selective electron contact, but facilitates the lateral collection of charge with low contact resistance when forming back contacts with Ag paste (Figure S32). We found that when the Ag paste was added directly to the TiO₂/Ga₂O₃ layer without ITO, the PEC efficiency was significantly decreased compared with the photoanode with ITO (Figure S33). This result indicates high contact (series) resistance at the back contact, which was also determined with the HF resistance in the EIS (Figure S29B).

The role of the front layers for efficient hole transport

To further explore photogenerated hole transfer in p-type Cu₂O photoanodes, we investigated the effect of the front layers, which play a critical role in the band bending at the semiconductor/electrolyte interface for facile hole transfer.

The water oxidation efficiency of the photoanodes was compared with three different configurations: Cu₂O (without any overlayers), Cu₂O/NiFe, and Cu₂O/Au/NiFe with the previously optimized ITO/TiO₂/Ga₂O₃ back contact layers. In LSV measurements, all electrodes showed PEC activity for water

oxidation, and the photoanode with Cu₂O/Au/NiFe front layers achieved the most improved onset potential of 0.86 V vs. RHE and a photocurrent density of 7.15 mA cm⁻² (Figures 5A and S34). This result suggests that Au, which has a higher work function than Ni, provides more favorable upward band bending at the Cu₂O/Au interface, thereby enhancing the charge transfer selectivity at this interface.^{28,45} However, we also found that the bare p-Cu₂O surface (typically depicted as having unfavorable downward band bending) was also able to perform PEC water oxidation, which is inconsistent with previous studies.^{23,46} The bare Cu₂O photoanode exhibited stable photocurrents for 25 h with approximately 91%–96% Faradaic efficiency in water oxidation (Figure S35), even without the additional co-catalysts, though the current was lower than with the metal contacts (Figure S36). These findings imply that the formation of a selective contact for minority carrier transfer (i.e., the back contact) is critical to perform PEC water oxidation at the front contact.⁴⁷ To confirm this hypothesis, we prepared a transparent, conductive back contact with nominally 4 nm-thick Au to form an ohmic contact and evaluated their PEC performance in water oxidation. In the LSV measurement, we found that PEC water oxidation was unfeasible using p-type Cu₂O with ohmic back contact (Figure S37). Moreover, the LSV curve showed high dark current after 0.8 V vs. RHE. An interesting consequence of the electron-selective contact at the back is that dark current is eliminated, which may be one reason why corrosion of the bare Cu₂O is much less severe than in previous studies.

As mentioned previously, the interface between Cu₂O and overlayers often acts as a recombination center. In particular, it is well known that metal layers on semiconductors can cause severe charge recombination at the surface of semiconductors due to either the presence of surface states or a high density of states in the metal near the mid-gap energy of the semiconductor.^{48,49} To mitigate this, we introduced a 1 nm Al₂O₃ layer on the Cu₂O surface using ALD to enhance charge separation efficiency through surface state passivation. The introduction of the 1 nm Al₂O₃ layer improved the PEC performance of both Cu₂O/Al₂O₃/NiFe and Cu₂O/Al₂O₃/Au/NiFe electrodes, which

Figure 6. DWE analysis to investigate steady-state open-circuit potential (OCP) in Cu_2O photoanodes

(A–C) DWE analysis of Cu_2O photoanodes with three different front layers of $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}$, and $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(3\text{ nm})/\text{Au}$. The colored line and black line represent the back potential (for electrons) and surface potential (for holes) of each photoanode, respectively. All electrodes featured an identical back contact layer of ITO/ TiO_2 / Ga_2O_3 .

(D–F) Schematic illustration depicting electron and hole transfer in each Cu_2O photoanode.

indicates that the Al_2O_3 layer effectively functions as a passivation layer (Figure 5B). To further explore the effect of the Al_2O_3 layer, we investigated its PEC performance by modulating the thickness of this layer. In LSV measurements, the photoanode with a 3 nm-thick Al_2O_3 layer showed a decreased PEC performance (Figure 5C). This result implies that the Al_2O_3 passivation layer must be thin (<1 nm) for hole tunneling from Cu_2O due to the deep-lying valence band position of Al_2O_3 . A thicker Al_2O_3 layer decreases the probability of tunneling, leading to reduced PEC performance.⁵⁰

DWE analysis to investigate the role of the Al_2O_3 layer

The role of the Al_2O_3 passivation layer was further elucidated through dual-working electrode (DWE) analysis. Cu_2O electrodes with three different surface configurations ($\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}$, and $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(3\text{ nm})/\text{Au}$) were prepared for this study. The optimized ITO/ TiO_2 / Ga_2O_3 layers were used as back contacts to establish the first electrical connection. A second contact was formed on the Au surface of the front layer using Ag paste and Cu metal, followed by covering with non-conductive epoxy to complete the DWE fabrication (see Methods section for details). This configuration enabled the investigation of

Fermi levels and quasi-Fermi levels of semiconductors, as well as the photovoltage of the photoanodes, under PEC conditions.^{51,52}

The DWE measurements commenced under dark conditions, where all electrodes exhibited identical potentials of approximately 0.82 V vs. RHE at both the surface and back contact. This is attributed to Fermi-level equilibrium between the internal junction of the Cu_2O photoanode and the redox species in the electrolyte (i.e., trace O_2 molecules) (Figures 6A–6C). Under illumination, however, distinct behaviors were observed for each electrode. For the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$ surface, the potential corresponding to the quasi-electron Fermi level at the back contact shifted from 0.82 to 0.12 V vs. RHE, while the quasi-hole Fermi level at the front layer showed negligible change. The photovoltage was measured at 0.7 V, which was defined as the difference between the quasi-hole and quasi-electron Fermi levels (Figure 6A). The $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}$ surface exhibited a similar trend to the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$ surface but demonstrated a higher photovoltage of 0.76 V (Figure 6B). In the case of the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(3\text{ nm})/\text{Au}$ surface, the photovoltage was reduced to 0.71 V, which indicates the increased recombination at $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ interface by sluggish hole tunneling through the 3 nm Al_2O_3 layer (Figure 6C).

Figure 7. PEC performance of Cu_2O photoanodes at neutral pH and the comparison of photocurrent density

(A) LSV curves of the Cu_2O photoanodes modified with optimized back contact and front layers in water oxidation and sulfite oxidation at pH 7.

(B) The stability of the Cu_2O photoanode in sulfite oxidation.

(C) The comparison of photocurrent densities of metal oxide photoanodes in PEC water oxidation. The numerical values below each circle indicate the corresponding supplementary reference (Tables S1–S3). The black arrows on the dashed blue line indicate the theoretical maximum photocurrent density for each metal oxide.

Based on our analysis, we propose the role of the Al_2O_3 layer. For the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$ surface without Al_2O_3 , charge recombination occurs to some extent at the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$ interface, resulting in a lower photovoltage (Figure 6D). For the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}$ surface, the Al_2O_3 layer effectively passivates surface states on the Cu_2O surface, reducing charge recombination and yet enabling efficient hole transport via tunneling, leading to a higher photovoltage compared with the $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Au}$ surface (Figure 6E). However, when the thickness of the Al_2O_3 layer is increased, the probability of hole tunneling is reduced, thereby leading to decreased PEC performance (Figures 6F and S38).

PEC performance of the Cu_2O photoanode in hole scavenger oxidation at neutral pH

We have confirmed that high performance in PEC water oxidation can be achieved by the p-type Cu_2O photoanode through charge carrier-selective engineering. However, the requirement for alkaline conditions and the slightly high onset potential may pose challenges for developing practical photoconversion devices. To address these issues, we evaluated the PEC efficiency of p-type Cu_2O photoanodes under neutral pH conditions and explored their PEC activity in sulfite oxidation, which typically demonstrates faster kinetics than for water oxidation.

First, we assessed the PEC water oxidation efficiency under neutral pH conditions using LSV measurements. The optimized Cu_2O photoanode was fabricated with back contact layers of $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3/\text{TiO}_2/\text{ITO}$ and front layers of $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}/\text{NiFe}$, with the NiFe activation via CV cycling under alkaline conditions prior to LSV measurements. In the LSV measurements, the Cu_2O photoanode exhibited an onset potential of 0.83 V vs. RHE and a photocurrent density of 6.0 mA cm^{-2} at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.5 M potassium phosphate (KPi) buffer solution (pH 7) (Figure 7A). The PEC performance was slightly lower than that observed under alkaline conditions due to the reduced catalytic activity of NiFe in neutral pH.

However, a significant improvement in PEC performance was observed in an electrolyte containing 0.25 M Na_2SO_3 in 0.5 M KPi buffer solution (i.e., sulfite oxidation). The Cu_2O photoanode showed an onset potential of 0.1 V vs. RHE and a photocurrent density of 10.7 mA cm^{-2} at 1.23 V vs. RHE (Figure 7A). It is noteworthy here that the remarkably low onset potential of 0.1 V vs. RHE was achieved, although some amount of current doubling was observed during sulfite oxidation (Figure S39).⁵³

Additionally, while the Cu_2O photoanode showed a slight decreased photocurrent density in water oxidation during 15 h (Figure S40), it demonstrated excellent stability over 40 h in sulfite oxidation, with only negligible efficiency loss (Figure 7B). We

assume that this is due to the absence of gas bubble formation during sulfite oxidation, which prevents the detachment of the front layers, thereby improving the durability of the Cu₂O photoanode (Figures S41–S43).⁵⁴ In this regard, we anticipate that strategies aimed at enhancing gas bubble formation and detachment through surface treatments or focusing on alternative reactions such as biomass or ammonia oxidation could facilitate the development of more efficient and especially durable PEC devices using p-type Cu₂O photoanodes. Given that the Cu₂O photoanode already exhibits superior PEC performance in water oxidation compared with other n-type metal oxides, further research holds significant potential for advancing this PEC system (Figure 7C).

Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrate interface engineering to develop an efficient and stable p-type Cu₂O photoanode for solar water oxidation in both neutral and strongly basic electrolyte solutions. The use of ITO/TiO₂/Ga₂O₃ as back contact layers and Al₂O₃/Au/NiFe as front layers effectively addressed challenges associated with poor minority carrier transport and high charge recombination. The champion Cu₂O photoanode achieved a photocurrent density of 8.65 mA cm⁻² at 1.23 V vs. RHE, the highest so far reported for an oxide light absorber. Our findings highlight the importance of selective contact design in enabling efficient minority charge carrier collection, thereby demonstrating the viability of using p-type semiconductors as the photoanode for PEC oxidation reactions. Future research could build on these insights to explore alternative oxidation reactions or enhance the durability and the catalytic activity of photoanodes in water oxidation, paving the way for high-performance PEC systems for solar energy conversion.

METHODS

Synthesis of the polycrystalline p-type Cu₂O semiconductor

Cu₂O was synthesized using a thermal oxidation method based on our previous research.³⁰ Cu foil (thickness: 0.05 mm) was cut into 15 × 15 mm pieces and placed in a quartz tube furnace under a controlled flow of Ar and air. Under Ar flow, the Cu foil was heated from room temperature to 1,030°C and maintained at this temperature for 1 h. Then, air was introduced to replace the Ar flow to oxidize Cu foil to Cu₂O for 2 h. After oxidation, the Ar flow was reconnected, and further annealing was carried out at 1,030°C for an additional 2 h. Following the annealing process, the temperature was decreased to 500°C over 1 h and then allowed to cool down to room temperature under Ar flow. The as-prepared ten pieces of Cu₂O substrate were etched in 60 mL of ammonia hydroxide solution (Honeywell, ~25% NH₃ basis) for 1 h, then rinsed thoroughly with deionized water and dried under a nitrogen stream.

Deposition of back contact for Cu₂O substrate

Ga₂O₃, TiO₂, and ITO were deposited as back contacts of the Cu₂O photoanode. One side of the etched Cu₂O substrate was covered with Teflon tape to protect the front side, and the substrate was then placed in an ALD chamber (R200, Picosun) to de-

posit Ga₂O₃ and TiO₂. Bis(μ-dimethylamino)tetrakis(dimethylamino)digallium (STREM, 98%) and tetrakis(dimethylamino)titanium (Aldrich, 99.99%) were used as precursors for Ga₂O₃ and TiO₂ deposition, respectively. For Ga₂O₃ deposition, the reaction chamber and precursor temperatures were maintained at 160°C and 165°C. The valve of the Ga precursor was opened for 2.5 s (0.5 s dosing to the reactor and 2.1 s of increased line pressure using boost mode), followed by a 7.0 s N₂ purge. Subsequently, a 0.1 s pulse of H₂O was introduced, followed by a 4.0 s N₂ purge. This cycle was repeated 194 times (corresponding to ~0.77 Å per cycle) to obtain a 15 nm Ga₂O₃ layer. The TiO₂ deposition was carried out in the reaction chamber at 120°C, with the precursor heated at 85°C. The precursor was put with a 1.6 s pulse in boost mode, followed by N₂ purge. A 0.1 s pulse of H₂O was then introduced, followed by another 6.0 s N₂ purge. This process was repeated 1,860 times (corresponding to ~0.54 Å per cycle) to achieve a 100 nm thickness of TiO₂. After the ALD process, ITO was deposited using PVD with a radio frequency (RF) magnetron sputtering technique. The Cu₂O modified with Ga₂O₃ and TiO₂ was placed in the PVD chamber (PVD Products Inc.), which was evacuated to below 8.5 × 10⁻⁷ Torr. ITO deposition was conducted under the following conditions: 60 W RF power, 10 mTorr chamber pressure, 50 sccm Ar flow, and 30 rpm stage rotation without any heating process. The deposition was performed for 42 min to obtain a 150 nm ITO layer (corresponding to ~0.06 nm per second). The thickness of each layer was measured on a Si substrate using an alpha-SE ellipsometer (J.A. Woollam Co.).

Deposition of front layer for Cu₂O substrate

Al₂O₃, Au, and Ni were deposited as front layers on the opposite side of the back contact. The back contact layer was covered with Teflon tape, and the Cu₂O substrate was placed in the ALD chamber for Al₂O₃ deposition. Trimethylaluminum (Strem Chemicals, 98%) was used as the precursor for Al₂O₃. For the Al₂O₃ layer, the reaction chamber temperature was maintained at 120°C, while the precursor was kept at room temperature. The valve of Al₂O₃ deposition was opened for 0.1 s, followed by a 6.0 s N₂ purge. Subsequently, a 0.1 s pulse of H₂O was introduced, followed by another 6.0 s N₂ purge. This cycle was repeated 13 times (corresponding to ~0.77 Å per cycle) to get a 1 nm-thick Al₂O₃ layer. Following the ALD process, a 100 nm Au layer (corresponding to ~0.05 nm per second) and a 50 nm Ni layer (corresponding to ~0.07 nm per second) were sequentially deposited using a sputtering method (EM ACE600, Leica). The deposition conditions were as follows: 15 mA working current and 5.0 × 10⁻² mbar for the Au layer, and 38 mA working current and 2.0 × 10⁻² mbar for the Ni layer.

Fabrication of the Cu₂O photoanode

Cu₂O photoanode was fabricated using non-conductive epoxy resin (Loctite Epoxide-resin EA 9461 and EA 9466). First, Ag paste was applied to the ITO surface of the Cu₂O substrate in a hollow square shape (0.1–0.12 cm²), and a piece of Cu metal was connected to the square-shaped area using additional Ag paste. The extra surface outside the square area was blocked with opaque epoxy resin to ensure controlled light absorption. The Cu₂O substrate was then placed on a glass slide with the

back contact facing the glass, and the front layer was sealed with the epoxy resin again, leaving only the Ni surface (0.1–0.12 cm²) aligned with the square-shaped area on the back contact exposed.

Galvanic replacement of the Ni layer to form nickel-iron oxyhydroxides

Galvanic replacement of the Ni metal of the front layer was performed following a previous report.³³ Briefly, a 10 mM FeSO₄ solution (Aldrich, 99%) was prepared in deionized water with stirring for 15 min, and 100 μL of the FeSO₄ solution was then dropped onto the Ni surface for 40 min. Afterward, the Ni surface was rinsed with deionized water and dried under a N₂ stream.

PEC characterization

PEC characterization was performed using an SP-200 Bio-Logic potentiostat in a three-electrode configuration consisting of a photoanode, platinum wire, and Ag/AgCl as working, counter, and reference electrodes, respectively. A 150 W Xe lamp (LOT Oriol) equipped with an AM 1.5 G filter was used as the light source for PEC measurements (calibrated to 1 sun illumination using a standardized Si solar cell). For PEC measurement, 1 M KOH (pH 14) and 0.5 M KPi (pH 7) were used as electrolytes. LSV and CV measurements were performed at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. The produced oxygen of the photoanode was measured by an Inficon Fusion Micro gas chromatograph (Chemlys) with a molecular sieve column (10 m) and a μTCD detector. Argon was used as the carrier gas. The operation pressure was between 1.020 and 1.030 bar and kept constant with a pressure control system. The one-compartment cell was degassed for 30 min, and it was crosschecked by a GC measurement that no O₂ and N₂ were detectable. The calibration of the measured counts of produced mol O₂ was done by a two-electrode configuration with 2 platinum wires in the single compartment cell at different currents (10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 300, 500, 1,000, 2,000, and 5,000 μA), followed by a determination of the related mol per count. A three-electrode configuration was used for the GC measurement, and the sample was illuminated by a white light LED (ultrahigh-power lightguide-coupled LED, HCRI 5700K from Prizmatix) to reach a similar current as with “one sun” from our solar simulator. The gas chromatograph used in our measurements does not operate via direct syringe injection but instead uses a continuous sampling method with an Ar carrier gas line and a 10 m molecular sieve column. Oxygen evolution is monitored by periodically sampling a small internal gas volume (100 to 200 μL) from the PEC compartment cell every 2.5 min (with a dead volume due to the tubing of about 150 μL). There is a time delay for the first GC cycle due to the time required for oxygen to saturate the electrolyte solution and for the gas from the measurement cell to reach the detector (by the periodic sampling of the gas chromatograph). Monochromatic light for IPCE measurement was produced using a home-built double monochromator with a halogen light source. The light intensity of the monochromator was calibrated using a Si diode. EIS measurements were performed using an SP-300 Bio-Logic potentiostat with an AC amplitude of 10 mV and a frequency range from 0.2 Hz to 1 MHz. The bias potential steps were approximately 50 mV, with an equilibrium time of 30 s at

each step. For the measurement, a white light bias was applied using LEDs (SP-12-W5, cool white Luxeon Rebel). The EIS data were fitted using Zview software.

Physical characterization

The surface morphology was analyzed with a Zeiss Gemini 450 SEM. High-resolution XPS spectra of the photoanodes were obtained by a Physical Electronics (PHI) Quantum 2000 X-ray photoelectron spectrometer featuring monochromatic Al-K_α radiation, generated from an electron beam operated at 15 kV and 35 W. The energy scale linearity of the instrument was established through calibration with a reference sample of Au. The elemental composition maps in the cross-section were obtained by TEM at a Talos 200FX equipped with a SuperX (Bruker). The samples for TEM measurement were prepared by focused ion beam (FIB) at a Helios 5 UX.

DWE measurement

First, an additional contact (second contact) for surface potential measurement of Cu₂O front layer was formed on the Au layer of the Cu₂O photoanode surface using Ag paste and Cu metal. The Ag paste and Cu metal were coated with epoxy resin (Epoxide-resin EA 9461, Loctite) to protect direct contact with the electrolyte. Open-circuit potential (OCP) measurements were performed using a DWE setup via a Bio-Logic SP-300 bipotentiostat. The back contact (i.e., first contact) and front contact (i.e., second contact) of the Cu₂O photoanode were connected with each working electrode (WE1 and WE2), and the Fermi level and quasi-electron/hole Fermi levels were monitored under dark and light illumination conditions, respectively.

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead contact

Requests for further information, resources, and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, S. David Tilley (david.tilley@chem.uzh.ch).

Materials availability

This study did not generate new materials.

Data and code availability

All datasets obtained in this study have been deposited at Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.17131610](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17131610)

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, S.B. and S.D.T.; methodology, S.B. and S.D.T.; investigation, S.B.; formal analysis, S.B., T.M., D.Y., and P.Z.; writing – original draft, S.B.; writing – review & editing, S.B., T.M., D.Y., P.Z., and S.D.T.; funding acquisition, S.D.T.; resources, S.D.T.; supervision, S.D.T.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

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